

Epidemiological, Clinical Characteristics and Comorbidities Among Deceased Patients with COVID 19 Infection: A Retrospective Study

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess epidemiological, clinical characteristics and comorbidities among deceased patients with COVID-19 infection.

Methods: The Retrospective study among deceased patients with COVID-19 infection at Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India for COVID-19. The study included patients who succumbed to COVID-19 for the period of two years.

Results: The mean age was 58.02 years and there was a male (70%) preponderance among the study population. Majority of patients were elderly, 61–80 years of age group (41%). The mean duration of illness was 5.5 days. The most common comorbidities among the deceased were diabetes (46%) and hypertension (40%) followed by chronic kidney disease (26%), coronary artery disease (8%), and COPD (12%). The mean duration of hospitalization was 4.2 days. Among clinical parameters, majority (65%) of patients had tachycardia (heart rate >100/min). Most of the patients who presented to the hospital had respiratory rate >24/min (92%) and mean oxygen saturation of 68% at room air. The most common symptoms at the time of presentation were breathlessness (93%) and fever (75%) followed by cough (35%), myalgia, and fatigue (24%).

Conclusion: Majority of the patients who contracted the illness and died due to COVID-19 were elderly, males with diabetes and hypertension. At the time of presentation, the majority had respiratory distress of acute onset. Elderly population with comorbidities is more prone to disease and has higher chances of respiratory failure and death.

Keywords: Comorbidities, COVID-19, Hypoxia, Bihar, Pandemic.

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Introduction

The 2019-nCoV causing an ongoing outbreak of respiratory illness called novel coronavirus pneumonia which has infected many populations till date. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), a novel infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), [1] has become a global

public health concern as the number of deaths due to COVID-19 continues to increase. In February 2021, the COVID-19 mortality rate was estimated to be roughly 3% globally. [1] It has resulted in millions of deaths even in India. However, data on intensive care mortality in the Indian population has been sparse. [2] Clinical

spectrum of SARS-CoV-2 infection ranges from asymptomatic or mild, self-limiting respiratory tract disease to severe progressive pneumonia leading to acute respiratory distress syndrome and death. The proportion of patients with severe illness requiring admission to an intensive care unit (ICU) has been reported to be between 4 and 32%.[3] The clinical features and severity of COVID-19 vary among individuals, based on multiple factors, such as age and associated comorbidities.[4] Asymptomatic COVID-19 patients may not require hospitalization.[5-7] However, severe cases, for example, patients with systemic inflammation, pneumonia, hypoxemia, and peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂) of < 92%, require hospitalization. Patients with severe COVID-19 may become critically ill with acute respiratory distress, shock, myocardial injury, heart failure, coagulation dysfunction, and acute kidney injury, all of which may lead to death.[8] Knowledge of the epidemiological and clinical features of patients who demise due to COVID-19 is needed for a better understanding and proper management of the disease, and these features have been evaluated in a few studies.[9] Realizing that there are little data and inadequate mortality assessments in a COVID-19 Indian ICU setting, we embarked upon this study to describe clinical characteristics, outcomes, and factors associated with mortality in patients with COVID-19 requiring intensive care in a tertiary care hospital in Bihar, with very limited resources.

The aim of the present study was to assess Epidemiological, clinical characteristics and comorbidities among deceased patients with COVID 19 infection.

Materials And Methods

This study was conducted in Netaji Subhas medical College and Hospital, Bihar which is dedicated to COVID-19. It was a retrospective observational study. The epidemiological and clinical features of

patients presenting to this centre were recorded. A total of 1000 patients admitted in COVID ICU NSMCH who died during the hospital stay were taken in this study. Patients were diagnosed to have COVID-19 by reverse transcription-polymerase chain reaction at the Department of microbiology or referred from other facilities. The data were collected retrospectively from medical records and included demographic data, age, sex, smoking history, blood group, comorbidities, clinical symptoms, laboratory test results, radiological findings, treatment medications, and period of hospitalization. Comorbidities included diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease, chronic kidney disease, cancer, and obesity. The most prevalent clinical COVID-19 symptoms were fever, cough, dyspnea, chest pain, diarrhea, and confusion. The laboratory tests evaluated complete blood count, coagulation profile, and renal and liver function. The dates of COVID-19 diagnosis, hospital admission, and death were also recorded. The survival time during hospitalization (length of stay) was defined as the period between the date of admission and death. The Ethics Committee) granted ethical approval for the study to be conducted, and the research complied with the Declaration of Helsinki. Consent was waived as data were anonymous and collected retrospectively (secondary data).

Statistical Analysis

Data entry and analysis were performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences® software.¹⁵ The categorical variables were presented as percentages, and the continuous variables were described using mean ± standard deviation (SD) for the normally distributed variables and the median (interquartile range [IQR]) for the non-normally distributed variables. The chi-square test was used to assess any significant associations between the categorical variables. The independent-

samples t-test was utilized to compare differences in the mean between the groups (adjusted for age and BMI). The paired-samples t-test and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test were applied to compare any differences over time for the normally and non-normally distributed independent continuous variables, respectively. A

binary logistic regression model was explored the predictors of mortality during the early stay in hospitals. The Cox regression for survival analysis was also investigated the effect of predictors upon the time of mortality during the early stay in hospitals. A p-value of <0.050 was statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Baseline characteristics

Characteristics	N%
Male	700 (70)
Female	300 (30)
Age (years)	
<20	20 (2)
21-40	120 (12)
41-60	400 (40)
61-80	410 (41)
>80	50 (5)
Mean age±SD	58.02±12
Duration of illness (days)	
1-3	280 (28)
4-6	350 (35)
7-9	220 (22)
>10	150 (15)
Mean duration of illness (days)±SD	5.5±2.4
Comorbidities	
Diabetes mellitus	460 (46)
Hypertension	400 (40)
Chronic kidney disease	260 (26)
Coronary artery disease	80 (8)
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	120 (12)

The mean age was 58.02 years and there was a male (70%) preponderance among the study population. Majority of patients were elderly, 61–80 years of age group (41%). The mean duration of illness was 5.5 days. The most common comorbidities among the deceased were diabetes (46%) and hypertension (40%) followed by chronic kidney disease (26%), coronary artery disease (8%), and COPD (12%).

Table 2: Clinical characteristics at presentation

Characteristics	N%
Heart Rate	
<100	350 (35)
>100	650 (65)
Respiratory rate (/min)	
<24	80 (8)

>24	920 (92)
Oxygen saturation (%)	
>90	50 (5)
81-90	70 (7)
71-80	300 (30)
<70	580 (58)
Mean oxygen saturation(%)±SD	68±8.2
Symptoms	
Fever	750 (75)
Cough	350 (35)
Breathlessness	930 (93)
Sore throat	70 (7)
Myalgia/fatigue	240 (24)
Sputum	120 (12)
Diarrhoea	110 (11)
Duration of hospitalization (days)	
<1	350 (35)
1-5	500 (50)
>5	150 (15)
Mean duration of hospitalisation (days)±SD	4.2±1.8

The mean duration of hospitalization was 4.2 days. Among clinical parameters, majority (65%) of patients had tachycardia (heart rate >100/min). Most of the patients who presented to the hospital had respiratory rate >24/min (92%) and mean oxygen saturation of 68% at room air. The most common symptoms at the time of presentation were breathlessness (93%) and fever (75%) followed by cough (35%), myalgia, and fatigue (24%).

Discussion

First case of Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) was reported in Wuhan, China in December 2019. Soon the disease spread to most countries of world and was declared Global pandemic by World health Organization on 11th March 2020.[10] In India the first case of COVID-19 was detected on January 30, 2020 in a 20 year old female who had returned to Kerala from Wuhan, China.[11] Mortality rate due to COVID-19 vary across regions but

WHO estimates global mortality to be about 3% of cases.[12]

The mean age was 58.02 years and there was a male (70%) preponderance among the study population. Majority of patients were elderly, 61–80 years of age group (41%) similar findings were reported by Grasselli et al[13] from Italy among 1591 patients infected with COVID-19 where 82% of the patients were male. The mean duration of illness was 5.5 days. The most common symptoms at the time of presentation were breathlessness (93%) and fever (75%) followed by cough (35%), myalgia, and fatigue (24%). Bhandari et al[14] in their study observed Fever (48%) as the most common symptom followed by cough and shortness of breath.

The mean duration of hospitalization was 4.2 days. Among clinical parameters, majority (65%) of patients had tachycardia (heart rate >100/min). Most of the patients who presented to the hospital had respiratory rate >24/min (92%) and mean

oxygen saturation of 68% at room air. The most common comorbidities among the deceased were diabetes (46%) and hypertension (40%) followed by chronic kidney disease (26%), coronary artery disease (8%), and COPD (12%). In a similar study published in New York by Richardson et al[15] among 5700 patients hospitalised with COVID-19 infection, the most common comorbidities were hypertension (56.6%), obesity (41.7%), and diabetes (33.8%). The mean duration of illness at the time of admission was 5.5 days supported by the study done by Zhao et al[16] on 77 patients with a median time of illness onset to the admission of 5 days.

Conclusion

The present study provides an insight into various epidemiological and clinical parameters of patients who succumbed to COVID-19. It could be observed that elderly patients with comorbidities were more prone to contracting the virus and had a more severe disease progression. Majority of the patients who contracted the illness and died due to COVID-19 were elderly, males with diabetes and hypertension. At the time of presentation, the majority had respiratory distress of acute onset. Elderly population with comorbidities is more prone to disease and has higher chances of respiratory failure and death.

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